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Large-scale electronic surveillance and watch lists: The products of paranoid politics?

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Abstract

We know from the articles of Richard Hofstadter that a defensive, even paranoid style has pervaded American politics from time to time. Murray Edelman and Michael Rogin have shifted the psychological aspect of this terminology to a political one, focusing on how the construction of a political spectacle can incite hysteria and paranoia to attract public attention and by so doing engender a securitisation that expands the executive powers of the state. Rogin describes how American political discourse has emphasised counter-subversive strategies in the construction of enemies; for example, against Aboriginal peoples, communists and the USSR, and more recently, illegal migrants and terrorists, who are supposed to have infiltrated the homeland. However, the implications of such politics have rarely been expanded to transnational or international politics.

The broad objective of this paper is to link the configuration of contemporary world politics with interesting strands of sociological research coming from the critical study of American politics. More specifically, the author argues that the compilation of watch lists from transnational databases criminalises travellers as illegal and dangerous migrants, while also affecting everyone who uses cloud computing. States use a paranoid style to play off national sovereignty against their international obligations. Each country's practices in this regard constitute a distinctive variation of the trend toward Global Preventive Surveillance (GPS), which has, in the author's view, become a contemporary form of a transnational process of (in)security, i.e. a process that delivers insecurity through technological tools aiming to provide security.

To sustain this argument, the paper shows how the emergence of global watch lists is re-orienting database technologies to serve the ends of electronic mass surveillance. Governments justify mass surveillance, despite its illegal status in many countries, by claiming that if everyone is doing it, it cannot be illegitimate. A paranoid strain of transnational politics based on unease and fear is thereby instrumentalised in the name of sovereignty, security, citizenship and national identity. Watch lists, in the author's view, are a concrete manifestation of the development by security professionals of a transnational stock exchange of fears, which purports to focus on migrants and border control but has much more to do with fostering domestic counter-subversive strategies than with serving as an effective response to threats.

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Large-scale electronic surveillance and watch lists: the products of paranoid politics?

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Framing the problem: Is large-scale surveillance of information and human mobility a form of transnational political paranoia?

The aim of this paper is to link the configuration of contemporary world politics with the most interesting strands of sociological research offered by a critical study of American politics. The paper argues that compiling watch lists from transnational databases criminalises travellers and also affects people around the world who use cloud computing. What is the contemporary rationale to justify surveillance on this scale? Where and how is surveillance performed? How is it transformed into intelligence tools through watch lists? And how did it become so pervasive that it threatens to transform everyday life? For many, these questions have a simple answer: everything derives from the imperative to struggle against global terrorism. I argue here that the close connection between surveillance and intelligence is not the result of a legitimate fear but of paranoid politics in the sense that Michael Rogin gives to the term when discussing McCarthyism.

Section I therefore delves into American critical sociological debates about McCarthyism, where concepts such as political demonology were devised. The works of Richard Hofstadter (Hofstadter, 1996) on the development of a paranoid style in American politics, and its elaboration by Michael Rogin who shows that this paranoid politics may originate within the security apparatus of the state, are pivotal to understanding contemporary politics and the surveillance of mobility. (Rogin, 1967; Rogin, 1987; Rogin, 2002)¹

Although the analysis of these authors was restricted to American politics, the rationale of large-scale international electronic surveillance of people and information also has a decidedly transnational character today, because Western intelligence services share bulk data on the movements, communications, and contacts of people, across as well as within national borders. Section II traces the connections between intelligence services, border guards, and anti-terrorist initiatives. Although they now act across a transnational field of power, US services are *primus inter pares*. Despite this asymmetry, no one intelligence service can collect global data without collaborating with other services. These structural links have challenged national politics and traditional concepts of national security. As argued elsewhere (Bigo, 2013) this has created transnational guilds of security professionals, networks obsessed with technology and secrecy that collaborate across borders, justifying the mass collection of data in the name of threats from a supposed enemy within. This logic connects large-scale surveillance in democracy with the kind of paranoid politics best illustrated by the 'one per cent (1%) doctrine' of Donald Rumsfeld, the Defense Secretary in the George W. Bush government from January 2001 to December 2006.² Such strategies are aimed at creating compliance in populations that might otherwise contest a preventive strategy that requires the collection of large-scale data and mass surveillance. This section will focus on two specific programmes, the one concerning the movement of persons

¹ Ronald Rogin: *Le Monde*, 11 September 2002 (partly reproduced).

² The 1% doctrine is explained on page 20 of this article. For a long explanation of its origins and impact see Suskind, R. (2006) *One Percent Doctrine: Deep inside America's Pursuit of Its Enemies since 9/11*. Simon and Schuster.

and border control, and the online movement of information and correspondence (particularly its interception, collection, retention, and extraction for profiling).³

Following this, section III first analyses the no-fly lists constructed through the surveillance of movement of persons with the Passenger Names Records (PNR) and then discusses the secret surveillance by the NSA, GCHQ⁴, and other Western intelligence services of the movement of digitised information and correspondence, as disclosed in the Snowden revelations. I argue that these two programmes share certain characteristics. First, their initiators claim that these programmes give them a global reach, allowing the prevention of unexpected threats through the sharing of information through collaboration between intelligence services, a claim not confirmed by recent inquiries. Second, the sharing of information creates a 'hybridisation' of the intelligence services' apparatus with that of private providers – be they airline companies, travel agencies, or private internet providers. This 'competence creep' allows private interests to be involved in the making of national security and generates intrusion into personal life that goes beyond data protection and even privacy because it affects the nature of the democratic regime.

Finally, I argue that if surveillance, intelligence, and democracy are not *per se* incompatible, the unprecedented scale of surveillance that electronic tracking provides to the intelligence services (affecting the freedom of movement of people, goods, money, travel, and the freedom of communication concerning information data, metadata, and routes) has created a form of paranoid transnational and bureaucratic politics dominated by security professionals and their networks across private and public spheres. The interconnection of private and public databases, I argue, is not due to technological progress or increased global threats, but to a veneration of technology that threatens to transform (Marx, 1988) the nature of democratic regimes.

I) Suspicion on a transnational scale? Fear, the politics of fear, and paranoid politics

I-A: Lessons of McCarthyism: paranoid politics and political demonology

In his analysis of McCarthyism, Hofstadter contends that a form of popular thinking, coming from the margins but relayed by some politicians, may change the logic of liberalism by focusing on certain fears to the extent that they become obsessions. He distances himself from the psychological definition of paranoia, insisting that his focus is not on individual personality traits but on a style of politics.

"Style has to do with the way in which ideas are believed and advocated rather than with the truth or falsity of their content". (Hofstadter, 1965, p.5 op. cit.).

³ A third logic is connected with the movement of capital and freezing of assets. This has been described by Anthony Amicelle and Marieke de Goede. It concerns the movement of capital and freezing of assets that assembles the flow and traceability of 'dirty' money and the limiting of assets available to organised crime and terrorists. Popular media sources have sought to familiarise the public with organisations that strive to freeze terrorist assets, such as the SWIFT company, the TFTP, and the UN. In addition, a long list of organisations (including banks), have collected information on private individuals for the purpose of detecting suspicious transactions.

⁴ See annexe 1.

This style is characterised by the emergence of a spokesperson who is able to popularise the conviction that, beyond the group that recognises the spokesperson, everyone, even those who disagree, is in danger of attack by unseen threats and enemies. The spokesperson channels this anxiety through tales of enemies and conspiracies out to destroy the nation and its way of life. Populist rhetoric arises from the instrumentalisation of public fears by the extreme. Conspiracy theories may differ depending on the place, the circumstances, and historical periods, but the style remains constant. For Hofstadter the political parties of the far left and the far right are the most susceptible to use this rhetoric, but not liberals.

Michael Rogin, in his critique of Hofstadter, developed the notion of paranoid politics from a different angle (Rogin, 1967; Rogin, 1962). For Rogin, paranoid politics is not an effect of populism produced by people living on the margins and threatening liberals, it is a product of a kind of counter-subversive politics that constructs objects of fear through specific policies in order to provide justification for a series of measures that would otherwise be rejected. The question is less about ideology than the practice of governing through fear. For instance, governments, including liberal ones, may use paranoid rhetoric to justify increasing the budget against perceived security threats, thereby freeing the executive branch from the oversight of watchdogs, especially courts (Viltard, 2001). McCarthyism is but one example of this strategy that Rogin calls 'political demonology' (Rogin, 1967). Political demonology is a way of understanding government by fear, either by developing a politics of counter-terrorism justifying revenge, or by a politics justifying itself through protection of victims, or freedom of people. The images of the enemy are sometimes built on the idea of an enemy within subverting a regime, or by a more subtle focus on the weaknesses of a society, the need to resist all forms of dangers, be they coming from enemies outside, within, or even from abstract forces.

Rogin, fifteen years after his analysis of McCarthyism, used a similar analysis to explain Ronald Reagan's actions in the 'covert war' his administration conducted against Nicaragua in 1986. The Reagan administration articulated a political demonology where the enemies were terrorists and drug traffickers, and ushered in the idea of a permanent global threat, which had to be 'rolled back'. In a change from previous US rhetoric, Reagan conflated the idea of national security and foreign affairs with the survival of the everyday life of the US citizen at home, because of a threat coming from abroad that citizens were unaware of. Rogin presents therefore a genealogy of counter-subversive politics organised by security bureaucracies, a political demonology (Rogin, 1988) in American politics that dates from the demonisation of Indians by the army to the red scares promoted by the FBI, to the Cold War and demonisation of socialist policies. This double exclusion permits us to understand the enemy not as a prohibited ideology but as a foreign idea infiltrated into a government that generates traitors. The McCarthy period led to a brand of politics that is still popular in the US (and elsewhere), whereby right-wing politicians accuse any powerful person on the left of being unpatriotic, a communist, or socialist sympathiser. The ensuing witch-hunts create numerous 'false positives': that is, innocent people who are wrongly accused, and a small number of substantiated cases. As documented later, oversight by intelligence services began as a reaction to McCarthyism, but paranoid politics was nevertheless practised against the civil rights movements of the 1960s and used again to justify Ronald Reagan's actions in Nicaragua in the late 1980s.

I-B: The war on terror as global McCarthyism?

Shortly before his death in September 2002 Michael Rogin wrote an article about President Bush's 'war on terror', analysing the president's narrative as a follow-up to that of Ronald Reagan, but with the figure of the terrorist serving as a global enemy, simultaneously internal and external, and the threat raised to an Armageddon-like fight against evil. Rogin saw this as a strategy that would link right-wing isolationism and the religious right with interventionist politics that required a new military focus on internal security and the development of tools of mass surveillance (Rogin, 2002). Global watch lists can perhaps be read as merely the acceleration and accentuation of this logic. Nevertheless, I will argue that the construction of watch lists on a transnational scale is evidence that American-style paranoid politics has gone global through a process that involves less a national political ideology of an American imperialism than the constitution of transnational links between security bureaucracies in the West that promote the idea of a global danger.

II) The 1% doctrine and the globalisation of paranoid politics by security professionals

II-A: Justification of the war on terror: technologising watch lists

As we know from the declaration of 14 September 2001 on the 'war on terror', new modes of surveillance were justified as a necessary response to the catastrophic events of 9/11. However, the list of catastrophes to be guarded against quickly expanded, from terrorism to weapons of mass destruction to cyber terrorism (the disruption of the electronic circulation of money) and so on, creating a major narrative of suspicion (Aradau and Munster, 2011). While such a narrative is not new – its cultural imagery has flourished for decades in the US – the scale of suspicion is unprecedented because the image of the suspect is so vague (Bigo, 2005; Bonelli, 2005; Ceyhan and Peries, 2001; Guittet et al., 2005). McCarthyism, shocking at the time, now looks to have been a small-scale affair. McCarthy claimed to have a list of traitors' names in his wallet. But the list he was talking about was around 20 persons. Now the director of the NSA will not brandish a paper list, he will have a small hard-drive with upwards of 400,000 suspects under active surveillance.

The Obama administration, despite moves to tone down the rhetoric of the war on terror, and to stop torture, has nevertheless followed similar security policies to the Bush administration, reproducing the reasoning of previous bold statements such as "the question is not if, but when" and "we have to act before it is too late" in a milder way, but without a change of the logic, as shown in the renewal of the Patriot Act by the Obama administration.⁵ The difference lies therefore more in the style than the content. The Obama administration has distanced itself from the paranoid style of politics while pursuing the same kind of policy, especially on large scale surveillance, and on providing even more money for NSA capabilities (see next section). It is necessary therefore to distinguish even more than Rogin the

⁵ May 26, 2011, declaration of President Barack Obama when he signed the PATRIOT Sunsets Extension Act of 2011, a four-year extension of three key provisions in the USA PATRIOT Act.

logic of political rhetoric and the logic of governing by unease of the transnational guilds of security professionals. The latter can continue as a legitimate practice as long as a new government does not criticise explicitly the previous one. A silence following a paranoid style of politics permits this politics to continue as normal behaviour for security professionals.

We can see for example that contemporary security professionals, even from the left, repeat the arguments of right-leaning intellectuals who emphasised in the 2000s that in the event of catastrophic world events, intelligence services could not be limited by concerns about privacy rights. For example, Posner contended that in such situations “the intelligence services must cast a wide net with a fine mesh to catch the clues that may enable the next attack to be prevented” (Posner, 2006, p. 5). And, as he explains, the intelligence services cannot be the firemen arriving after the fire, they have to act preventatively, and this can only be done by reversing the onus of proof and treating everyone as a potential terrorist until proven otherwise. The reasoning follows the one of Dershowitz on the use of torture with warrant (Dershowitz, 2007). The approach can be summarised as: if the consequences of the risk are immense, even if the probability of the risk is only one per cent, it is necessary to prevent the actions by following all populations deemed to be dangerous. This group is not pre-defined, it emerges from the search itself, and it is unfortunate, but necessary to protect the innocent, to ensure the net is wide enough to catch the potentially guilty.

Under this doctrine, a legitimate fear of a major incident (on the part of the government) justifies changing the behaviour of security agents and removing the presumption of innocence. This reasoning has been attributed to Donald Rumsfeld, whose ‘1% syndrome’ justifies surveillance not on the basis of risk assessments of past behaviour (insurance style of reasoning), but on an anticipation of the future consequences of a single catastrophic act.⁶ But now in 2014 most of the intelligence services of the West agree with this statement of Rumsfeld, as if it was not a contentious one but a truth coming from their watch lists themselves and from the technologies they use. In some ways the paranoid politics is not voiced anymore, but continues through the practices of bureaucracies and their technologies. Paranoid politics is buried through statistics. The national logic of American politics is concealed under a transnational exchange of information.

II-B: The consequences: a legitimate suspicion destabilising the principle of innocence? What does prevention mean?

As an official of the National Counter Terrorism Center I interviewed in 2005 put it, giving one of the soundest narratives of the choice to do prevention that I collected from my series of interviews during 2002 to 2009:

“We are in an era where if we have to choose to catch ten persons and to detain them indefinitely because one of them is potentially organising a terrorist act, then the nine innocent persons have to admit that their detentions are the collateral effect of the research of the good for the collectivity. Maybe the traditional notion of justice is reversed, but this is fairness to accept the sacrifice of some freedom for

⁶ This is where I disagree with a large part of the literature on risk assessment that mixed the two types of reasoning and created false continuities between the logic of insurance described by François Ewald and Michel Foucault and the logic of catastrophe described by Rumsfeld. For the explanation of Rumsfeld’s position and disagreement with other members of the Bush administration, see Suskind, R. (2006) op.cit.

the overall collectivity. The world has changed. To answer to global threats, we need new tools to survive. And we just apply a utilitarian principle: prevention. ... Prevention means to confront a list of suspects or suspicious behaviours with a larger list of persons or aliases, or categories of individuals sharing the same patterns that our algorithms have discovered as pertaining to a common profile: this is what we call watch lists...They are not public lists as the blacklists, which are used for individuals that we already know very well, they are for suspects, which have not been condemned. We do not punish them. We just refuse them *ex ante*, or at the border; and if we detain them it is for a very short period, we try to send them back as quickly as possible. What is wrong with that?"⁷

For him, it is not possible to act as before, under rules (of law), as these rules are "locking one arm behind the back of the members of the intelligence services" giving the advantage to the terrorists. When survival of the nation is at stake, accepting these limitations is no longer possible. Intelligence services in democracies have to be trusted absolutely by the people who have elected the government. They are working to protect them, not to spy on them. And they need to work in secrecy to protect them effectively. Criminal justice, the presumption of innocence, privacy, and freedom have to be adjusted to the new situation. Hidden fanatics have to be discovered and disrupted, whatever the cost for civil liberties.

Contemporary large-scale surveillance and the creation of huge lists of suspects seem to be the result of this syndrome of enlarged suspicion. Convergent inquiries by a series of NGOs and parliaments, both following the Snowden revelations and grounded in facts covering the past ten years, notably the inquiries into Total Information Awareness, suggest that the different lists work according to the will of bureaucracies and their private contractors, which continually reassess who can be trusted and who cannot. They are a product, a 'deliverable' objectivising suspicion by finding some of the presumed dangerous or undesirable 1% who *might* have been lethal for society.

Against this narrative, in the following sections I insist that this reasoning turns the logic of criminal justice on its head. By removing the presumption of innocence and constructing a logic of the future perfect (*futur antérieur*), it holds everyone suspicious on the basis of a 'forward memory' – a memory that has already read the future (Bigo and Delmas-Marty, 2012; Ugelvik and Hudson, 2012)⁸. But this claim is not justified on the basis of evidence – predictions of future behaviour are more oracle than science (Cassin, 2014).

Nevertheless, the lack of efficiency data is apparently no hindrance. Accepting the impossibility of presenting evidence of plots that were discovered and blocked through these tactics, governments, their intelligence services, and the courts and NGOs defending human rights appear to be deadlocked. The US government has already proposed some reforms, which would limit the capacity of the NSA to do bulk telephone and internet collection. In Europe courts have strongly criticised the bulk data collection and the data retention directive, but have thus far been unable (or unwilling) to declare preventive data collection illegal. This may be because transnational networks of intelligence agencies exchanging data on the suspects of

⁷Interview by Didier Bigo: American liaison officer in Europe 2008.

⁸ Which is not exactly the logic of speculative security as described by Marieke de Goede in 2013: de Goede, M. (2012) The Swift Affair and the Global Politics of European Security. *Journal of Common Market Studies* 50:214-30.)

other services have powerfully argued that these practices are essential tools to keep the world safe. But this has created a stock exchange of fear, where each organisation comes with its own watch list and entry refusals, and enters a series of transactions with the others, with the outcome depending on the relative power of institutional players. The so-called Five Eyes Group, the Club of Berne, or even Europol have become such places⁹. Once built, the system must grow, as this is a central rationale for these networks. Since it is taken for granted that millions of would-be terrorists are 'out there', if lists do not grow, governments might suspect that these agencies are not doing their job, a scenario that threatens both private and public players, involving a loss of profits, jobs, prestige, and career prospects (Hayes, 2013).

In addition, if some successes are not alleged, people are more likely to react against the controls. Therefore, list expansion must go beyond the obvious suspects to include those with only tangential ties, or none at all, to terrorist groups. The lists now incorporate individuals associated with other forms of behaviour deemed problematic by the authorities, such as criminal tax evaders, people with false documents, and over-stayers¹⁰. The dynamics exponentially increase suspicion and add to the number of travellers defined as suspects whose information gets exchanged and added to other lists.

III) Tracing and controlling by electronic means: a transnational and hybrid logic of the private and public that claims to have a global reach to prevent threats

Two kinds of suspicion-based, preventative programs – where an individual has to prove his/her innocence before he can travel or exercise the right of free speech – have been developed. Both rely on collecting information on mass populations, identifying categories of the unwanted, and checking them out through different intelligence services. Both generate automated watch lists of suspects that can be shared internationally and operated everywhere.

III-A: Tracing and controlling the circulation of persons: the making of no-fly lists

The first kind of programme concentrates on the creation of 'smart borders', accomplished through profiling and collecting personal data. In democratic countries this securitisation of borders has to be reconciled with the political economy of liberalism.

Smart borders are heralded for their ability to let people go 'freely' about their legitimate activities while electronically collecting information on all passengers. The programmes then check everyone's personal history and movements to distinguish the potentially dangerous traveller from the legitimate one. This divides travellers into the 'trusted' and the 'unwanted'. The first category of travellers will never see the controls or the remote surveillance, the second will end up on 'no-fly' lists and

⁹ See annex 1.

¹⁰ An overstay is a person who was granted limited leave to enter or remain in a country, but who neither left the country on the date indicated nor asked for the leave to be extended.

'terrorist watch lists', not because of what they have done, but because they match a profile of what others have previously done.

A variety of smart border programs (e.g., PNR-API- CAPPs-US Visit- or Schengen VIS and SIS, ESTA, Entry (and Exit) systems) exist both in the US and the EU. The labels are now familiar to frequent travellers, though only specialists understand the subtle differences between US and EU systems, their logic and justification¹¹. Both are justified by the need to combat terrorism, but European rationale also emphasises the battle against illegal migration and over-stayers. In the US, CAPPs I & II (Computer Assisted Passenger Pre-Screening System), set up after September 11 by the Department of Homeland Security, are the most important programmes. The US Secretary of Homeland Security, Michael Chertoff, for example, explained in 2006 that with the US-VISIT programs (followers of CAPPs II criticised for his very high number of false positives) the government has implemented a network of interconnected computers and interoperable databases with biometric entry capabilities at 117 airports, 16 seaports, and 153 land ports of entry. According to Chertoff: "within seconds, we can positively confirm a person's identity by checking their two digital finger scans against terrorist and criminal watch lists and immigration records." (Chertoff, 2006, p. 3)ⁱ.

This has created new controversy, not only about its efficiency, but also about the privacy of American citizens and foreigners passing through the US en route to non-US destinations. We still do not know the connections between this US-Visit program and PNR records, or how much personal information comes from unidentified government databases or from commercial sources. Nevertheless, some sources have suggested that they may be linked to NIMD (Novel Intelligence from Massive Data, an initiative of the secretive Intelligence Community Advanced Research and Development Activity – ARDA), which focuses on "massive data, and with MATRIX (Multistate Anti-Terrorism Information Exchange), a state-level program supported by the US Department of Justice that aims to give state law enforcement agencies across the nation a powerful new tool for analysing the personal records of both criminals and ordinary Americans. According to an article published in the *Washington Post* on 5 August 2003, this particular program "would let authorities ... instantly find the name and address of every brown-haired owner of a red Ford pickup truck in a 20-mile radius of a suspicious event"¹².

Speculation is high, knowledge is scarce. In an excellent Ph.D thesis Matthew Kabatoff of the LSE explored the technicalities of this logic of tracing travellers in detail (Kabatoff, 2013). As he explains, the most prevalent and high-profile method of watch-list matching employed by US security is known as the Terrorist Watch List, where all air travellers entering, exiting, and travelling within the United States have their name data matched against three lists (that are themselves compilations of other lists): first is the terrorist 'no-fly' list (a list containing, as of 2008, approximately 2,000 names of individuals who are barred from boarding an airplane with a US destination); second is the 'Automated Selectee' list, (a list containing approximately 14,000 names of individuals placed under additional scrutiny while crossing borders due to the perception by US intelligence of their ties to terrorism. Third, at least six other US governmental watch lists, containing

¹¹ See Annex 1.

¹² <http://cironline.org/reports/us-backs-florida%E2%80%99s-new-counterterrorism-database-%E2%80%98matrix%E2%80%99-offers-law-agencies-faster-access>

names of individuals who have committed immigration violations or other crimes, are checked¹³.

These computerised watch lists are considered by the DHS to be the real lines of control. The physical border is there to operationalise the intelligence gathered before a potential threat crosses the border. It is an important line, but the last one, not the first. These watch lists create the possibility of sorting people, requiring only some to be controlled at the airport – extending the time period of control but also avoiding extensive bottlenecks at the airport. However, this means that everyone travelling is submitted to procedures of trust verification. The supplementary information gathered through systematic watch-list checks creates a specific category of ‘others’: individuals who are less trusted than everybody else. The data of less trusted travellers, containing transaction authentication numbers, bank accounts, aliases, residence addresses, ethnicity, nationality, associates, and sometimes fingerprints) is flagged if the software detects any signs of ‘abnormal’ behaviour or suspect associations (even, for example, sitting near another suspect twice). These travellers are checked again at the airport and sent back if they are considered a danger to national security.

As explained by Taipale, a lawyer, scholar, and social theorist specialising in information technology, who serves at the Markle Foundation that has developed software for predictive data:

“The data-mining methods used as part of counter-terrorism and border security practices [are]: (i) subject-oriented – where an individual’s predicates are charted as part of a wider investigation; and (ii) pattern-based – where a set of pre-existing templates are applied to a data set, such as templates that would provide clues as to terrorist behaviour”. (Taipale, 2003)

In the second case, preventative data mining or data extraction-profiling is used. This is a methodological shift because statistics are not used for retrospective analysis, but for network and pattern analysis. Thus, while data from a specific individual can be extracted from a large number of agents in networks, a pattern, a trajectory, which seems to lead to a specific behaviour, can also be ascertained.

However, this claim to predict or even to detect is not effective. The match between databases connects them, but does not necessarily connect with actual behaviour or intentions. The US Department of Justice itself acknowledged this problem in 2005, stating that:

“Significant problems were identified. Our audit of the initial consolidation stage shows that further problems persisted in how the no-fly/selectee lists were used to match travellers’ names against each list. At the database level of the TSC, the DoJ found numerous errors in both how the transfer of watch-list names took place and how these names came to be coded in terms of their threat level. At the level of the algorithm, and the process used to match air travellers against the no-fly/selectee list, this was also

¹³ Databases used by the national terrorism center (NTC) to screen passenger name record (PNR) data 1 Advanced Passenger Information System (APIS), 2 Non-Immigrant Information System (NIIS), 3 Suspect and Violator Indices (SAVI), 4 Border Crossing Information System (BCIS), 5 Department of State visa databases, 6 TECS seizure data, and 7 Terrorist watch lists; subsets of the US government’s Terrorist Screening Database. Source: CRS Report 7-5700.

regarded as flawed although ultimately tolerable by the Government Accounting Office despite the fact that the algorithms used to match travellers consistently produced high rates of false positives. This acceptance of false positives signifies not only a turn towards precaution, but importantly the evidence of a government rationale that accepts collateral damage in respect to terror prevention; that is the sacrificing of individual rights or protections in order to provide the greater good of security as consistent with Posner and Vermeule." (DoJ quoted in Kabatoff, op. cit. p139).

The construction of watch lists as the practical element of a paranoid political strategy is not purely American, it is a transnational practice that applies on most of the (aerial) borders of Western countries. While the EU participated in the construction of watch lists, the International Civil Aviation Organisation has most vigorously promoted the development of computerised no-fly lists. Such lists put large segments of the global population under suspicion to enable the data mining that is needed to develop elaborate patterns and algorithms of prediction and construct profiles that take the form of watch lists (Weber, 2012).

The US government has been and remains the key player here. The Aviation and Transportation Security Act (ATSA 2001) requires the DHS and the Customs and Border Patrol (CBP) to collect and analyse passenger and crew manifests of foreign flights entering the United States. However, US actions have been followed, if not foreshadowed, by the European, with the Schengen Information System, and Australian counterparts with their entry-exit system. Both have developed even more systematic means of traveller information exchange. The history of the development of PNR and API negotiations worldwide has not been well documented, but the connections between research in the US, the EU, Australia, and at the level of international organisations demonstrate that the same logic is at work: information given to private operators (such as corporations) to improve service for consumers (such as loyalty cards) has been used at later dates by border control agencies to create watch lists and the like. After 11 September 2001, the logic of the 'one per cent doctrine' has pushed governments to extend the number of agencies supplying data and reorganising data collection to emphasise predicting future acts of terrorism rather than checking already known individuals. The PNR have been transformed from a useful tool for gauging consumers' choices into a security device that collects these choices to detect patterns of dangerousness from them. Although the examples given below show that the process is often arbitrary, incomplete, and inaccurate, it has nevertheless been presented systematically as successful in keeping the world safe from terrorism and illegal migration. All of these factors – the creation of the Department of Homeland Security; the rise in the number and power of the border control and immigration agencies; the compulsory participation of commercial airlines and travel agencies; the overall computerisation of visa deliveries and entry procedures (ESTA) – have mobilised thousands of personnel, all of them heavily invested in the development and growth of the industries of surveillance.

At the institutional level, the budgets and profits of private companies and agencies now depend on sustaining and growing the surveillance industry. Instead of a precise list of dangerous terrorists, identified by cooperation between services, and a specific target, identified by cross-checking that list against the list of travellers, today we have databases that collect, store and exchange data on all travellers in the hope of singling out terrorism suspects, despite the fact that the precise characteristics of terrorists are unknown. Data searches on subject-oriented relations have multiplied the possibilities of being identified on a terrorist list

because only one subject criterion needs to fit the overall definition. The anthropologist Mark Maguire has described in detail the logic of some of these counter-terrorist technologies. FAST (future attribute screening technology), for example, attempts to detect potentially dangerous subjects by ascertaining their mental state through technologies that measure cardiovascular reactivity, bodily secretions and eye movement. As he explains, the software can accurately detect stress, but the inference from emotional effect to dangerousness/terrorism is highly inaccurate, producing a very high rate of false positives. No one has been successfully convicted of terrorism after having been stopped by the machine (Maguire 2013, see also on San Diego airport; Bigo, 2008) Most scholars in behavioural sciences reject the claims of success made by security industry companies and their clients, in part because all of their evaluations are kept confidential. It is reasonable to suspect that confidentiality is deemed necessary because the evidence does not support the discourse of prevention or the logic of the one per cent doctrine.

Indeed, security analysts have used actor network theory (ANT) in their evaluations, but applied it without accepting the radical uncertainty that is its exploratory episteme. They have tried to transform it into proofs and explanatory arguments in order to justify a preventive logic. But ANT emphasises that depictions of the 'real' are merely one of many possible visual interpretations, not the truth, especially if the end result is so singular that the result is correlated with one specific individual. Clearly, criminal justice and ANT methodology of exploratory approaches cannot go together. Security analysts have relied on numbers, data mining, and threat visualisations as a truth independent of them, while at the same time they were constructing it. They are pushed by the need for results that the discourse of intelligence agencies need to deliver, while recognising in private that it is not a reliable technique and that nobody can predict the behaviour of an unknown person. The belief in predictive technology transforms the world into a fantasy land populated by intelligent machines. Thus, the behavioural machines, the software of network theories, and data mining have reframed the notion of terrorism, extended it to fit popular methods while transitioning away from initial targets. It has not been a solution to terrorism, but a product of the politics of fear of terrorism where technologies of profiling are used to 'neutralise' or mask the discrimination that is induced in the politics of suspicion. The transnationalisation, the hybridisation of public and private, the use of computer interoperable databases operate as forms of de-responsibilisation of the products of the political demonology of the watch lists. This is even more the case with the tracing and control of the circulation of digitised information.

III-B: Tracing and controlling the circulation of information in cyberspace: PRISM and large-scale electronic surveillance

The second kind of programme that shows this logic of suspicion is the one concerning the tracing, bulk collection, gathering, retention, and analysis of all the means of communication through the exchange of electronic data on anyone remotely connected with individuals already under surveillance, or those considered as useful targets for purposes of national security. The programme, or more precisely the series of programmes of interception of communications, have been kept secret for nearly a decade, but the revelations of Edward Snowden, published by the *Guardian* and the *Washington Post* on 6 June 2013, have revealed the scale of surveillance, the intrusiveness of intelligence, and the nature of our regimes. Snowden showed firstly that US authorities are accessing and processing the

personal data of EU citizens on a large scale via, among others, the National Security Agency's (NSA) warrantless wiretapping of cable-bound internet traffic (UPSTREAM), and through direct access to the personal data stored in the servers of US-based private companies such as Microsoft, Yahoo, Google, Apple, Facebook, and Skype (PRISM)¹⁴. This allows US authorities to access both stored communications as well as perform real-time collection on targeted users. Cross-database search programs such as UPSTREAM, PRISM, QUANTUMINSERT, BULLRUN, DISHFIRE and X-KEYSCORE, to name six of the most publicised programs, represent the tip of the iceberg of the NSA's surveillance. Secondly, the UK intelligence agency, Government Communications Headquarters (GCHQ), has cooperated with the NSA and initiated actions of interception under different programmes, code-named TEMPORA and OPTIC NERVE. Further reports have emerged implicating a handful of other EU member states that may be running (Sweden, France, and Germany) or developing (potentially the Netherlands) their own large-scale internet interception programs, and collaborating with the NSA in the exchange of data. But this collaboration is uneven and certainly not intended to build trust between the different services as the US has spied on its closest allies while asking them to collaborate, in order to verify what they were giving spontaneously and what they were hiding from the NSA. They have tapped into the cable going through the Middle East run by the French Orange company's wiretapping systems. Orange has launched a claim against the NSA for violation of private communications¹⁵. As a riposte, France has been accused of developing a rough model of QUANTUMINSERT under the codename of BABAR, which it is said to have used against Canada and perhaps the US. Angela Merkel complained to the NSA when it was proved that her mobile phone had been tapped for many years in the hope of securing an economic and political concession from the US. She compared this surveillance to that conducted by the Stasi, the infamous intelligence service run by the East German government until it was overthrown in 1989. Thirdly, beyond member state governments, institutions of the United Nations as well as EU institutions and EU member state embassies and representatives have been targets of US-UK surveillance and spying activities. For example, the UK's GCHQ infiltrated Belgacom systems through simulated LinkedIn access in what was codenamed (ironically or not) 'Operation Socialist' to gain access to the data of European Union institutions (the Commission, Council, and Parliament). It seems therefore that the NSA is often but not always the originator of this large-scale surveillance, and that most of its operations are performed via transnational networks of agencies that cooperate with or without the knowledge of their own governments. The questions concerning PRISM, Tempora and many other programs shared by the NSA, GCHQ and other intelligence services are extraordinarily important for security, sovereignty, alliance, international law, compliance, 'subjectivisation' of citizens, digital rights for all internet users independently of their nationalities (Bauman et al., 2014). To illustrate this, I will draw on the recent research I conducted for the European Parliament (Bigo et al., 15-10-2012)¹⁶.

¹⁴ This part is an excerpt coming from my own contribution to the note for the European Parliament: "National programmes for mass surveillance of personal data in EU Member States and their compatibility with EU law" <http://bit.ly/1chI2TJ>

¹⁵ http://www.lesechos.fr/30/12/2013/lesechos.fr/0203214421104_nsa---orange-se-porte-partie-civile-apres-le-piratage-d-un-cable-sous-marin.htm

¹⁶ See the two notes for the European Parliament: National Programmes for Mass Surveillance of Personal Data in EU Member States and their compatibility with EU Law (2013): PE 493.032, The US National Security Agency (NSA) surveillance programmes (PRISM) and Foreign Intelligence

This research highlighted three characteristics shared by these communication inceptions. First, they are secret operations that directly affect the daily life of all populations using internet services (such as email, web browsing, cloud computing, social networks, or Skype communications via personal computers or mobile devices), by transforming them into potential suspects. This is especially problematic for those who are not protected by citizenship rights within the country from which the surveillance originates, falling within the categorisation of 'foreign intelligence'. Second, they have a large scale, which changes their very nature, as they largely go under what was once called targeted surveillance with a warrant. These operations now plug into intelligence capacities using different forms of surveillance and different platforms, and may lead to data mining and mass surveillance.

A third characteristic, even more central and important, is that they are a hybrid of private and public forms of co-surveillance. This particular characteristic is unique to surveillance by electronic and cyber systems. A large part of the world's electronically transmitted communications, including, increasingly, information stored or processed within cloud computing services (such as Google Drive, Dropbox, Salesforce, Amazon, Microsoft, and Oracle) may be intercepted via technologies put in place by a transnational network of intelligence agencies that specialise in data collection, the leader of which seems to be the NSA. The NSA carries out surveillance through various programmes and strategic partnerships. While the largest percentage of internet traffic is believed to be collected directly at the root of the communications infrastructure (by tapping into the backbones of telecommunications networks distributed around the world), the recent exposure of the PRISM program has revealed that the remaining traffic is tapped through secret data collection and data extraction from nine US-based companies: Microsoft, Google, Yahoo, Facebook, Paltalk, Youtube, Skype, AOL, and Apple. Therefore, the surveillance programs not only imply the involvement of governments and a network of intelligence services, but also the 'forced' participation of internet providers through a Public-Private-Partnership (PPP).

On the basis of the provisions of the US FISA Act, the NSA, with an annual certification of the FISA court (FISC), can target any non-US citizen or non-US legal resident located outside the territory of the US for surveillance. These data, once intercepted, are filtered and suspect information is retained by the NSA and GCHQ. The stored data can then be aggregated with other data, and be searched via specifically designed programs such as X-KEYSCORE. Furthermore, internet access providers in the US (and also in Europe) are under obligation to keep their data for a certain period, in order to give law enforcement agencies the opportunity to connect an IP address with a specific person under investigation. The legal obligations concerning access to data and privacy law derogations vary according to several factors, including the affiliated internet providers and intelligence services, and the nationality of the persons under suspicion relative to the nation conducting the investigation.

The publication of Snowden's revelations in the *Guardian* and *Washington Post* generated much controversy about the legitimacy of this form of data collection. It became apparent that large-scale harvesting of data has to be understood along a continuum of intelligence service activities intricately linked to and embedded in the

activities and interests of their private contractors. First, data harvesting is used sometimes in the context of counter-terrorism or counter-espionage activities that follow criminal justice logic, but this is far from being the whole picture. Second, the counter-terrorism activities often proceed to the identification of unknown persons related to an initial group of suspects, within what is called three degrees of separation (or hops). That is, for a suspected person with 100 friends at the first hop, the person in charge of surveillance at the NSA or one of its private subcontractors can, without warrant, put under surveillance all 2,669,556 potential connections at the third hop¹⁷. Third, data-mining practices are used for cyber-spying activities that target specific groups in a military strategic approach, which is not interested in specific individuals and their personal data, but collects anonymous data to discern trends on general population behaviour. Finally, electronic mass surveillance activities are sometimes carried out without clear objectives, but they are stored in case they might be useful in the future, for the services' uses or for information regarding consumption variations or opinion modifications (including those that are political and religious).

Considering these varied uses and justifications, it becomes clear that the key question is the nature, scale, and depth of surveillance that can be tolerated in and between democracies. This is where the move to paranoid politics that allows the branch of the executive power to free itself from oversight is central because it affects the very nature of the regime.

IV) Surveillance, intelligence services, and democracy

IV-A: An old relation inside 'open societies'

Surveillance of populations is not a new phenomenon in liberal regimes. Specific groups of individuals have often been targeted by intelligence services because they were suspected of conducting criminal activities (including political violence). If democratic regimes have not gone as far as authoritarian ones, where intelligence bodies systematically spy on their own populations to detect dissent, (such as the STASI in the GDR, the Securitate in Romania, or the UDBA in former Yugoslavia), they nevertheless have a history of large-scale surveillance.

The purposes and scale of surveillance are at the core of what differentiates democratic regimes and police states. Even if there have been transgressions in the past, in principle intelligence services in democratic regimes do not collect mass data on large groups within the population. Furthermore, if surveillance is undertaken on specific individuals, it must be legally justified as necessary to detect and prevent violent actions, not merely to gather information on lifestyles or

¹⁷ Barack Obama, following one of the 45 recommendations of the review group on intelligence and communication technology, delivered December 12, 2013, seems ready to limit the search without warrant to two hops (in this case 16340), reducing the scale of the search while keeping the principle alive. Speech 179/01/2014, available online at the Guardian. <http://www.my-rss.co.uk/feeditem.php?feed=0&word=&search=laws&item=263734> Accessed 19/03/2014. For an interactive search on hops, see <http://www.theguardian.com/world/interactive/2013/nov/01/snowden-nsa-files-surveillance-revelations-decoded#section/1>. Accessed 19/03/2014

political opinions. This informal agreement, a shared understanding between the state and its citizens, is well illustrated in this quote:

“Our government in its very nature, and our open society in all its instinct, under the Constitution and the Bill of Rights automatically outlaws intelligence organisations of the kind that have developed in police states.” (Allen Dulles, 1963, p 4).

Nevertheless, when ramparts against full surveillance are not monitored regularly, they may stop operating. In the name of the development of high technologies and their possible use by ‘enemies’, intelligence services have crossed these boundaries in pursuit of their missions. This overstretching of national security can be partially attributed to a frequent redefinition of who is the enemy (or the suspect), and how far s/he is already perceived to have infiltrated the territory. However, in democracies, where separation of power is expected, the excesses of intelligence services have been regularly denounced when their unlawful activities were uncovered.

Prior to PRISM, US authorities were condemned on numerous occasions for spying on and infiltrating certain groups. For instance, civil rights movements and communists were targets in the 1950s, and the anti-war movement became a focus in the 1960s and 1970s. Secret programmes that used informants, intercepted mail and phone calls, and engineered break-ins, COINTELPRO in the late 1950s, as well as CHAOS and MINARET in the 1960s and 1970s, were all later condemned as unlawful surveillance programs. And they all gave rise to specific rules to protect US persons from these forms of political surveillance. The Foreign Intelligence Surveillance Act (FISA) court was specifically designed in 1978 to counterbalance these restrictions and give the judiciary the power to oversee proclaimed ‘foreign intelligence’ activities, especially those seen as affecting fundamental rights of US citizens. As detailed elsewhere, this court has constantly seen its powers undermined, even more so after 9/11 and the launch of the war on terror¹⁸. The court’s scope is also limited to the protection of US citizens; non-US persons who are victims of unlawful surveillance are excluded. Current PRISM and other NSA activities, and those of other intelligence services and private companies in the US, all demonstrate the weakening of the powers of the judiciary over intelligence activities. Implementing state or parliamentary oversight over such activities is further complicated by the participation of private players and corporations in global surveillance initiatives.

In Europe, a series of scandals emerged when undercover policing and surveillance of political parties endangered civil liberties, but they were more often connected with infiltrations and undercover operations than mass surveillance. In Spain, the creation of the GAL (Grupos Antiterroristas de Liberación) to fight the Basque separatist group, ETA, ended up with the condemnation and imprisonment of the former Minister of Interior in 1996. In France, the Renseignements Généraux were threatened with closure after a series of illegal activities, including phone-taps and the presumed assassination in the 1990s of a gay activist Pasteur Doucé, were revealed. More recently, in June 2013, Luxembourg’s Prime Minister Juncker officially announced that he would resign following a spying scandal involving the

¹⁸ Adam Schiff and Todd Rokita, “Republicans and Democrats agree: Fisa oversight of NSA spying doesn’t work ‘Secret law’ is anathema to our democratic traditions and the rule of law. We have introduced legislation to change this”, *The Guardian*, 29 July 2013.

illegal bugging of politicians, but did not, and has now been appointed as president of the European Commission.

Although controversial and difficult, the need for oversight of intelligence activities by parliamentary or judicial authorities has been widely accepted since the late 1990s. French intelligence services only recently agreed to an external control procedure. The Renseignements Généraux have partly survived under the DCRI, but their missions have been re-oriented. These services always insisted that they either focused on specific cases of spying or political violence, or that they were undertaking opinion polls that were better than those researchers and private companies could provide. As detailed below, the specificity of large-scale surveillance challenges these supposedly reassuring statements and raises questions about the connections between services in charge of antiterrorism and those in charge of collecting data for large-scale surveillance.

The war on terror that was launched after 9/11 shook the fragile consensus that democracies do not carry out mass surveillance and must accept judicial oversight. In the US, and to a lesser degree in Europe, a series of programmes have been initiated in secret using existing resources of modern information technology. The possibilities of surveillance have increased at the same pace as the increase of data availability. Regular increases in bandwidth have enabled new uses of the internet, such as mass storage and processing of personal, private, and governmental data through cloud computing. The development of mobile computing devices (e.g., Smartphones and tablets) has similarly provided a new wealth of geo-localised, personal information.

Each time a scandal occurs, as in the Swift- and TFTP-related scandals and their EU-US repercussions, the demand for the oversight of intelligence activities by parliamentary and/or judicial authorities gains more legitimacy. Clearly, the modalities and implementation of oversight remain problematic, because surveillance programmes, as documented in this article, are transnational and have a global reach, but also because these services surround their activities with a veil of secrecy (the 'classified information' argument). The alleged difficulty in drawing a line between the interests of the state and those of a specific party or political group (when these are not purely private interests) only adds to the current problem. In addition, when the programmes are conducting worldwide surveillance on citizens of other states, without the knowledge of these citizens, and even sometimes without the knowledge of their governments, the question is no longer one of data protection and individual privacy, but the survival of democracy itself.

IV-B: Mass surveillance in democracy via the generalisation of suspicion, prevention and watch lists: a change of scale that affects the nature of the regime?

What has to be seriously questioned here is the possible transformation of large-scale surveillance limited to terrorism into what can be called a 'cyber mass surveillance' that enables warrantless access to data on an unprecedented scale. Such surveillance, I argue, threatens the nature of the liberal regime.

Ironically, it was the European Parliament's inquiries into NSA's ECHELON program in 2000 and 2001 that revealed that surveillance programmes were capable of global communication interception and content inspection of telephone calls, faxes, e-mail, and other data traffic. As reported to the European Parliament by the whistle-blower Duncan Campbell, ECHELON was one part of a global surveillance system involving the cooperation of satellite stations run by the UK, Canada,

Australia, and New Zealand. Of particular concern was Campbell's report that ECHELON had moved away from its original purpose of defence against the Eastern Bloc and was being used for purposes of industrial espionage (Campbell, 2000).

Since ECHELON, a series of programmes has been initiated in the US and in Europe since 2004, with the development of integrated platforms, the breaking of software encryption keys, and the adoption of new software permitting routine filtering, all of which allow unprecedented amounts of data and metadata to be visualised and correlated. These new surveillance resources, the widespread use of Smartphones and the development of cloud computing have blurred the line between 'targeted surveillance' – justified by the fight against crime – and data mining, which carries the risk of limitless extension of surveillance. These programmes have been justified by the will to protect the population from crimes, and were tailored to provide tools for the profiling of categories of people likely to commit them. However, once data became available for search and extraction, other purposes for their use arose. One such attempt to broaden the scope of surveillance, the "Total Information Awareness" (TIA) program, was rejected by the US Congress in 2003 on the ground of 'function creep', and the programme was (at least publicly) limited to Terrorism Information Awareness (Harris, 2010). Yet the idea of warrantless wiretapping as well as blanket data searches has been carried out. Though strongly denounced in US Congress by Senator Ron Wyden, the TIA programme did not disappear, and was *de facto* legalised in 2007 by the Protect America Act. The mode of justification for the TIA is central as it is within this justification that a form of paranoid politics lies, making the link between the doctrine of the 1% and its implementation at the heart of designing interconnected systems of databases for predictive patterns. What is extraordinary when one reads the TIA document is that it assumes a one-to-one correlation between the physical world and the electronic world. At its core is the belief in the capacity of probabilistic calculation via algorithms, through models of predictive analytics that link the past, present, and future to find what cannot be found in the physical world – that is, a definitive prediction of the future. This belief, and the politics of fear that feeds it, is grounded in a political imagination that predicts chaos if surveillance is limited in any way. The chaos to come is multifarious – the terrorist with a nuclear bomb in a bag, the invasion of foreigners profiting from the hospitality of those who have accepted them, the possibility of drastic climate change, the destruction of the market economy, and the possibility of viruses jumping from animals to persons in a large-scale epidemic. Each of these scenarios is supposed to be prevented by the collection of ever more data. Safety cannot be assured, however, if the organisations in charge are constrained by judicial warrants and congressional limitations.

This belief was articulated by John Poindexter, who was at the heart of the 'Contra-gate' scandal in Nicaragua, and later the head of the Information Awareness Office under George W. Bush, in the document called Total Information Awareness (a document that may be the equivalent of Jeremy Bentham's panopticon for the modern age). Poindexter saw his proposal of visionary reform blocked by the US Congress in December 2003, but his efforts laid the groundwork for present day surveillance. The principles governing this new reality are that the system is only checking specific targets, persons already suspected for good reasons, but that the collection of data generally does not harm individuals who have nothing to hide. Liberty is therefore not at stake, since only criminals need to be worried. Information awareness has to connect all the dots to avoid loopholes and that is why total information awareness is necessary. The software is becoming so

intelligent that predictive analytics discerning emergent patterns via algorithms can discover patterns that mere human beings cannot. Specific associations can be visualised and used to prioritise threats.

TIA was finally refused but only because the emergence of prediction markets (betting on where the next attacks in the US would be) was considered unethical by Congress. Despite this, it seems that the horizon of awareness has been established, and that every argument against it represents an old-style liberal resistance that has to be overcome. Total Information Awareness has been renamed Terrorism Information Awareness, limiting its purposes to the fight against terrorism, organised crime and threats to national security. However, other programmes have been set up to circumvent these restrictions and join the dots with terrorism black lists and watch lists, border controls, as well as the internet and telecommunications. The recent revelations of NSA activities (e.g., PRISM and Xkeyscores) seem to demonstrate that continuity exists between TIA and the programmes that preceded and followed it. This raises a central question: how far does PRISM (in the US) and Tempora (in the UK) follow the logic of the TIA, the blueprint of the 1% syndrome and the doctrine for a paranoid politics? Do these two programmes maintain a purpose limited to terrorism and crime or are the data used also for tax evasion, for the advantage of private companies in their pursuit of contracts, for profiling the political opinions of groups considered marginal, or for elaborating scenarios concerning political conflicts and international situations?

Concern has increasingly centred on the perception that these programmes are interconnected and that some European member states' services participate in internet data extractions for multi-purpose 'explorations.' Snowden indeed claimed that data collected by the Tempora program is shared with the NSA and that no distinction is made in the gathering of data between private citizens and targeted suspects. But GCHQ has strongly insisted that they were not using data for indiscriminate searches, and that their use was restricted to national security, specifically the detection and prevention of crime. One may ask: where is the 'red line' that intelligence services in democratic regimes cannot cross when they use cyber surveillance and, if a red line is recognised, is it shared by the US and the EU? What can the oversight bodies on both sides do if they have in front of them a network of intelligence agencies and private providers, a transnational guild of professionals of unease?

Conclusion

Large-scale surveillance and mass surveillance: the link through paranoid politics

This article has underlined the fact that we now have evidence of the differences between the scale and depth of the programmes that are connected to PRISM and the Five Eyes Plus Group, in comparison with the programmes previously undertaken in the name of counter-terrorism and counter-espionage. Coming back to the central question: is this large-scale surveillance a form of paranoid politics that may endanger democracy? It is a question worth taking seriously. This means that a way of seeing the world and of expressing oneself is becoming known to and shared by groups who are framing these activities in terms of security and risk. This represents a transformation of everyday politics. Therefore, the

comparison with other periods, among them the emergence of McCarthyism, is useful. While this comparison may seem too strong, it constitutes a genealogy of paranoid politics that may emerge from large-scale surveillance. These 'products' are the result of the emancipation of control of the different guilds of (in)security professionals and intelligence services through the construction of a political demonology that created first a demonic figure: the suspect who has to be prevented from acting by anticipating and predicting his or her behaviour, and silenced through the use of statistics, algorithms, transnational exchange of information.

This figure of the suspect is not specifically one of a criminal enemy (internal or external). Here the boundaries of crime and enemy are themselves destabilised. The image is not naturalised through nationalism and patriotism, it is a test that each individual, responsible for his own freedom, has to pass before joining the group of trusted people who have the right to be protected from others. Therefore, obtaining knowledge concerning people's actions and thoughts by intelligence services is legitimate. It does not affect anyone's freedom, it is said, because the intent is not to spy, as in undemocratic regimes, but to verify if the person can be trusted. Furthermore, this test has to be done repeatedly, as the person may change over time. If the test is passed (beginning with the authentication of identity via biometrics and verification of narrative through information given compared with information stored on the databases), the person is normalised-certified and will join the happy travellers, benefiting from the world services of home through the internet. If not, if doubt is maintained, the person will be watched, 'abnormalised' (without being transformed immediately into an enemy or a person to exclude) and entered into data under one of the many categories that signal behaviour that may lead in the future to a crime or a terrorist act.

It is in this process that the justification of large-scale surveillance emerges, which plugs intelligence services and counter-terrorist services into the world of information exchange. Their capacities to connect what has been captured unintentionally or for other purposes by the heterogeneous assortment of techniques of surveillance and self exposure in social networks are considered normal, just because they are technologically possible. It also provides the rationale for collecting large amounts of information concerning travellers by 'smart' machines rather than face-to-face dialogue. The 'smartness' is a technical process of certification permitting a person to be trusted in order to avoid further control and to accelerate their travel. The person depends on his or her data double, as rejection implies watch-list classification.

It is of the utmost importance to understand the techniques of the integration platforms and the rationale under which the large-scale collection of personal data is permitted (the localisation of people, mapping their relations, identification of their coordinates to a specific group of 'suspects' in order to connect where they travel, where they (or their computers) are, with whom they speak, what they say, and who they are). This is a specific form of surveillance that is not captured by the academic debate between the centralist vision of the panopticon versus the decentralised and heterogeneous means of surveillant assemblages. This debate seems old fashioned, as the figure of the suspect who has to be certified at each step, and the development of platforms of data integration have to find a way to be organised simultaneously via the notion of large-scale data collection for targeted searches. The paranoid style is now pervading the technical language and is less glittery, but more in depth in term of the government of populations.

Glossary

Club de Berne is an intelligence sharing forum between the intelligence services of the 28 states of the European Union (EU), Norway and Switzerland, named after the city of Bern. It is an institution based on voluntary exchange of secrets, experience, and views as well as the discussion of problems. The Counter Terrorist Group (CTG) is an offshoot of the Club and shares terrorism intelligence. It provides threat assessments to EU policy makers and provides a form for expert collaboration. CTG, like the Club, is outside of the EU's institutions but communicates with them via the participation of the EU Intelligence Analysis Centre (EU INTCEN). Although it is outside the EU, its presidency rotates in line with that of the EU Council presidency and acts as a formal interface between the Club de Berne and the EU.

Europol (short for European Police Office) is the European Union's law enforcement agency that handles criminal intelligence. Europol has no executive powers. It is a support service for the law enforcement agencies of the EU member states and delivers strategic analysis coming from the exchange of information on terrorism (TESAT) and organised crime (SOCTA). It became fully operational on 1 July 1999. Europol allocates its resources (800 staff, of these, approximately 145 Europol Liaison Officers (ELOs)) from its headquarters in The Hague. The size of Europol belies the fact that they are in constant liaison with hundreds of different law enforcement organisations, each with their own individual or group seconded to assist Europol's activities. As of 2013, Europol covers all 28 member states of the European Union. In order to fight international organised crime effectively, Europol cooperates with third countries and organisations. The 15 third countries are (in alphabetical order): Albania, Australia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Canada, Colombia, Iceland, Republic of Macedonia, Moldova, Norway, Russian Federation, Serbia, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, and the USA.

Five Eyes: often abbreviated as 'FVEY', refers to an Anglophone alliance comprising Australia, Canada, New Zealand, the United Kingdom, and the United States. These countries are bound by the multilateral UKUSA Agreement – a treaty for joint cooperation in signals intelligence. In the late 1990s, the existence of ECHELON was disclosed to the public, triggering a major debate in the European Parliament and, to a lesser extent, the United States Congress. As part of efforts to win the ongoing War on Terror since 2001, the FVEY further expanded their surveillance capabilities, with much emphasis placed on monitoring the World Wide Web. The former NSA contractor Edward Snowden described the Five Eyes as a "supra-national intelligence organisation that doesn't answer to the laws of its own countries". Documents leaked by Snowden in 2013 revealed that the FVEY have been intentionally spying on one another's citizens and sharing the collected information with each other in order to circumvent restrictive domestic regulations on spying.

GCHQ: Government Communications Headquarters (GCHQ) is the British intelligence agency responsible for providing signals intelligence (SIGINT) and information assurance to the British government and armed forces.

NSA: National Security Agency of the United States of America. This US intelligence agency is responsible for global monitoring, collection, decoding, translation, and analysis of information and data for foreign intelligence and counter-intelligence purposes – a discipline known as signals intelligence. NSA is also charged with

protection of US government communications and information systems against penetration and network warfare.

PNR: in the airline and travel industries, a passenger name record (PNR) is a record in the database of a computer reservation system (CRS) that contains the itinerary for a passenger, or a group of passengers travelling together. The concept of a PNR was first introduced by airlines that needed to exchange reservation information in case passengers required flights of multiple airlines to reach their destination ('interlining'). For this purpose, IATA and ATA have defined standards for interline messaging of PNR and other data through the "ATA/IATA Reservations Interline Message Procedures – Passenger" (AIRIMP). There is no general industry standard for the layout and content of a PNR. In practice, each CRS or hosting system has its own proprietary standards, although common industry needs, including the need to map PNR data easily to AIRIMP messages, has resulted in many general similarities in data content and format between all of the major systems.

When a passenger books an itinerary, the travel agent or travel website user will create a PNR in the computer reservation system it uses. This is typically one of the large Global Distribution Systems, such as Amadeus, Sabre, Worldspan or Galileo, but if the booking is made directly with an airline the PNR can also be in the database of the airline's CRS. This PNR is called the Master PNR for the passenger and the associated itinerary. The PNR is identified in the particular database by a record locator.

SIS: the Schengen Information System (SIS) is a governmental database used by European countries to maintain and distribute information on individuals and pieces of property of interest. The intended uses of this system are for national security, border control, and law enforcement purposes. A second technical version of this system, SIS II, is now in place under the responsibility of the European Commission. There are more than 46 million entries (called alerts) in the SIS, mostly covering lost identity documents. Person alerts make up around 1.9% of the database ($\approx 885,000$ records) each containing information items such as: first and last names, middle initial, date of birth, sex, nationality, any aliases they may be using, whether the person in question was armed and/or violent, reason for the alert, action to be taken if person encountered.

A transaction authentication number (TAN) is used by some online banking services as a form of single use one-time passwords to authorise financial transactions. TANs are a second layer of security above and beyond the traditional single-password authentication. TANs provide additional security because they act as a form of two-factor authentication. Should the physical document or token containing the TANs be stolen, it will be of little use without the password; conversely, if the login data are obtained, no transactions can be performed without a valid TAN.

Bibliography

- Aradau, Claudia, and Rens van Munster. (2011) *Politics of Catastrophe: Genealogies of the Unknown*. Prio New Security Studies. London, New York: Routledge.
- Bauman, Zygmunt, Didier Bigo, Paulo Esteves, Elspeth Guild, Vivienne Jabri, David Lyon, and R.B.J. Wlaker. (2014) 'After Snowden, Rethinking the Impact of Surveillance', *International Political Sociology* 2/2014:forthcoming.
- Bigo, Didier. octobre, 2008 Dans Les Filets Du Contre-Terrorisme Global. *Le Monde Diplomatique*, 26-28.
- . (2005) La Mondialisation De L'(in)Sécurité. *Cultures et Conflits, spécial ELISE : Suspicion et exception*:pp. 53-101.
- . (2013) The Transnational Field of Computerised Exchange of Information in Police Matters and Its European Guilds. In *Transnational Power Elites: The New Professionals of Governance, Law and Security*, p. 155: Niilo Kauppi, Mikael Madsen.
- Bigo, Didier, Gertjan Boulet, Caspar Bowden, Sergio Carrera, Julien Jeandesboz, and Amandine Scherrer. (15-10-2012) *Fighting Cyber Crime and Protecting Privacy in the Cloud*. Commissions : Espace De Liberté, De Sécurité Et De Justice: European Parliament.
- Bigo, Didier, and Mireille Delmas-Marty. (2012) Prédiction Et Prévention : Conversation. In *To Be Published*. New York-Montreal.
- Bonelli, Laurent. (2005) Un Ennemi 'Anonyme Et Sans Visage'. Renseignement, Exception Et Suspicion Après Le 11 Septembre 2001. *Cultures&Conflits*:101-30.
- Campbell, Duncan. (2000) Inside Echelon: The History, Structure, and Function of the Global Surveillance System Known as Echelon. *Telepolis . , Mr*.
- Cassin, Barbara. (2014) *Derrière Les Grilles (D'évaluation)*. Fayard/Mille et une nuits.
- Ceyhan, Ayse, and Gabriel Peries. (2001) L'ennemi Intérieur : Une Construction Politique Et Discursive, Construire L'ennemi Intérieur. *Cultures & Conflits*:3-11.
- Dershowitz, Alan M. (2007) *Preemption: A Knife That Cuts Both Ways*. WW Norton & Co.
- Guittet, Emmanuel-Pierre, Miriam Perier, Didier Bigo, Laurent Bonelli, and Collectif. (2005) *Suspicion Et Exception*. Editions L'Harmattan.
- Harris, Shane. (2010) *The Watchers, the Rise of America's Surveillance State*. New York.
- Hayes, Ben. (2013) How International Rules on Countering the Financing of Terrorism Impact Civil Society. *CIVICUS (2013), State of civil society*:117-26.
- Hofstadter, Richard. (1996) *The Paranoid Style in American Politics, and Other Essays*. 1st Harvard University Press pbk. ed. Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University Press.

- Kabatoff, Mathew Alexander Yuri. (2013) Subject to Predicate, Risk, Governance and the Event of Terrorism within Post-9/11 U.S. Border Security. In *sociology*, p. 168: LSE.
- Marx, Gary. (1988) La Société De Sécurité Maximale. In *Deviance et Societe*.
- Rogin, Michael Paul. (1967) The Intellectuals and Mccarthy: The Radical Specter.xi, 366.
- . (1962) Mccarthyism and Agrarian Radicalism. pp. vii, 341 l. n.p.,: University of Chicago.
- . (1988) *Ronald Reagan, the Movie and Other Episodes in Political Demonology*. [Pbk. , 1988]. ed. Berkeley, Calif.: University of California Press.
- . (1987) *Ronald Reagan, the Movie and Other Episodes in Political Demonology*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- . 2002 The War on Evil. partly reproduced in Le Monde 11 September.
- Taipale, Kim A. (2003) Data Mining and Domestic Security: Connecting the Dots to Make Sense of Data. *Columbia Science and Technology Law Review* 5:1-83.
- Ugelvik, Synn© ve, and Barbara Hudson. (2012) Justice and Security in the 21st Century : Risks, Rights and the Rule of Law. *Routledge studies in liberty and security*.
- Viltard, Yves. (2001) Le Cas Mc Carthy. Une Construction Politique Et Savante. *Cultures&Confits*:13-60.
- Weber, Cynthia. (2012) Design, Translation, Citizenship: Reflections on the Virtual (De) Territorialization of the Us–Mexico Border. *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space* 30:482-96.
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